

Ecofeminist grand narratives? Cohabitability with more-than- human worlds

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abstract

Small-scale narratives, whether scientific, literary or artistic, are the vehicle for much, if not most, of our contemporary philosophical reflection on climate change. Such stories are essential in allowing us to think through, and within, our circumstances. Yet they often struggle to articulate, let alone to answer, the bigger questions at stake: how to redraw our ontological maps to make the world more habitable for humans and nonhumans alike? How to enact collective political action to create a life-affirming future on our planet? This article makes two, somewhat provocative, claims. Firstly, that the reclamation of grand narratives is vital to produce viable ecological futures, despite metanarratives' bad reputation. Secondly, that such reclamation has already begun to take place, albeit tacitly, within ecofeminism. This paper sketches the key concepts and parameters of the ecological grand narratives emerging in contemporary ecofeminist thought. So doing, it demonstrates how ecofeminists allow us to rethink our position of being human on the planet and conceive of a more-than-human cohabitability on the grandest – and most effective – scale.

keywords: *universality, grand narrative, ecology, feminism, politics, cohabitability, ecofeminism, habitability, narrative*

I ntroduction

Grand narratives have a rather bad reputation, and not undeservedly so. Myriad feminist, postcolonial and post-structuralist thinkers have convincingly pinpointed their weaknesses, arguing that metanarratives are not only unable to make sense of the late twentieth century, but have also served as agents of marginalisation for non-dominant and vulnerable subjects. The French philosopher Jean-François Lyotard famously diagnosed such 'incredulity toward metanarratives' as our 'postmodern condition',¹ in which playfulness, ironic distance and relativism are the main aes-

¹ J-F. Lyotard, *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*, trans. by Geoff Bennington and Brian Massumi (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1984), p. xxiv.

thetic principles.² Half a century later, it is time to return to grand narratives once more.

Small-scale narratives, whether scientific, literary or artistic, are the vehicle for much, if not most, of our contemporary philosophical reflection on climate change in the environmental humanities.³ Such stories are essential in allowing us to think through, and within, our circumstances. Yet they often struggle to articulate, let alone to answer, the bigger questions at stake. As such, they cannot be used to effectively tackle the momentous challenge at hand: the need for a radical collective overhaul across all spheres of social life (economy, law, politics, culture). The climate crisis has provoked conceptual and political disorientation. In such exigent circumstances, we must ask: What stories should be told about human beings' place on the planet? How do we redraw our ontological maps to make the world more habitable for humans and nonhumans alike? How do we enact

² I follow Lyotard and use 'grand narratives' and 'metanarratives' interchangeably.

³ In recent scholarship in anthropology, sociology and philosophy, important work for the environmental humanities and its more-than-human approaches to the ecological crisis has been undertaken by, notably, M. de la Cadena, *Earth Beings: Ecologies of Practice across Andean Worlds* (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2015); V. Despret, *What Would Animals Say if We Asked the Right Questions*, trans. by Brett Buchanan (London and Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2016 [2012]); V. Despret, *Quand le loup habitera avec l'agneau* (Paris: Les Empêcheurs de penser en rond/ La Découverte, 2020 [2002]); D. Haraway, *When Species Meet* (Minneapolis and London: University of Minnesota Press, 2008); D. Haraway, *Staying with the Trouble. Making Kin in the Chthulucene* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2016); E. Kohn, *How Forests Think. Towards an Anthropology Beyond the Human* (Berkeley: California University Press, 2013); D. Bird Rose, *Wild Dog Dreaming: Love and Extinction* (Charlottesville: University of Virginia, 2011); A.L. Tsing, *The Mushroom at the End of the World. On the Possibility of Life in Capitalist Ruins* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2015); T. van Dooren, *Flight Ways: Life and Loss at the Edge of Extinction* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2014); E. Viveiros de Castro, *Cannibal Metaphysics: For a Post-Structural Anthropology*, trans. and ed. by Peter Skafish (Minneapolis and London: University of Minnesota Press, 2017 [2009]); E. Viveiros de Castro, *The Relative Native. Essays on Indigenous Conceptual Worlds* (Chicago: Hau Books, 2015), to name only a few.

collective political action to create a life-affirming future on Earth? With clear-sighted acknowledgment of their pitfalls, the possibility emerges to re-articulate the utility of grand narratives themselves, as we use them to productively reconceptualise human-nonhuman collectives. In all such work, however, it is essential to avoid falling back on previous schemes of thought that were problematic and exclusionary.

This article reclaims grand narratives as a philosophical ‘form’ or ‘genre’ by drawing on ecofeminist theory and praxis. It makes two, somewhat provocative, claims: firstly, that the reclamation of grand narratives is vital to produce viable ecological futures, despite meta-narratives’ (deservedly) bad reputation; secondly, that such reclamation has already begun to take place, albeit tacitly, within ecofeminism. This paper sketches the key concepts and parameters of the ecological grand narratives emerging in contemporary ecofeminist thought. So doing, it demonstrates how ecofeminists allow us to rethink our position of being human on the planet and conceive of a more-than-human cohabitability on the grandest - and most effective - scale. More broadly, this article is an invitation to a debate on how we can reclaim and reconfigure the genre of grand narrative for an age of ecological crisis.

The grand narratives of old

Grand narratives are stories about who we are and what we should do, not only as individuals but also as collectives. They explain our knowledge and experience by ordering them in larger cultural frameworks, thereby giving them meaning. Religious grand narratives are a particularly salient example. The narrative of the Garden of Eden and ‘the fall of man’ in the Old Testament is illustrative here. The story recounts how the first man, Adam, and the first woman, Eve, live in the paradise of Eden, until Eve is tempted by a serpent, eats the apple from the tree of knowledge and causes the couple’s banishment from the Garden. In this grand narrative, human beings are understood as sinful and (righteously) condemned to eternal suffer-

ing while on Earth. Men are the peak of all creation. As men were made in the likeness of God, it follows that they have ‘dominion’ over all the natural world. Women, in turn, are considered as bearers of Eve’s guilt and therefore are meant to be subordinate to men. They are weaker willed, with looser morals. They are the temptresses who lead good men astray, a motif that resurges across centuries in literature, visual arts and philosophy. This metanarrative has had an overwhelming impact on our societies: on gender roles, human sexuality, our attitudes to nature, our approach to life, ethics and politics. It has structurally preformatted how we understand ourselves as humans and our place on Earth. The Edenic story teaches us, notably, that the world’s creation was a finite act, and thus the planet does not need to be constantly maintained or taken care of. The Earth exists to be governed and ruled over according to the logic of domination.

In the secular realm, the grand narrative of modernity has, in turn, been crucial in our current relationship to nature. Modernity’s story is one of continuous, necessary progress towards a ‘better’ world through the means of science, technology and ‘civilisation projects’ in non-European countries. Its fundamental values are enlightenment, freedom, productivity and growth that – in the official version, at least – should benefit everyone. The vision of a human being offered in this grand narrative is characterised by sovereignty – that is, of individualism and independence from the natural environment, from the limits of materiality, even from other people. Such a sovereign subject has been championed by modern philosophy and – as many scholars have argued – has contributed to our ecological crisis today.⁴ In the grand narrative of modernity, then, we are in the position of mastery over nature. More than that, we are said to be radically *different* from nature. Indeed, we are *better* than animals. We are special and unique due to our power to speak and reason (*logos*). Our mastery over nature has been, itself, ‘naturalised’.

⁴ See, notably, B. Latour, *We Have Never Been Modern*, trans. by Catherine Porter (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1993); B. Latour, *Facing Gaia: Eight Lectures on the New Climatic Regime*, trans. by Catherine Porter (Cambridge: Polity, 2017).

It is posited as an objective, and rather obvious, fact. In this metanarrative, the only way to overcome the ecological crisis is to tighten our technological grip on nature and attain total control over planet Earth. This is reflected in current ecomodernist approaches to the climate crisis, such as geoengineering.

In European cultures, and in many cultures of the Global North, the powerful grand narratives of Modernity and the Garden of Eden continue to structure our collective lives. Metanarratives are fundamentally performative and generative: they have the power to create realities and they are essential in the formation of communities.⁵ They activate speculative imagination and are necessary for political action. Therein lies their importance – or rather, the importance of their reclamation – in the age of climate crisis. The act of reclamation is particularly vital here. As Isabelle Stengers points out:

Reclaiming is an adventure, both empirical and pragmatic, because it does not primarily mean taking back what was confiscated, but rather learning what it takes to inhabit again what was devastated. Reclaiming indeed associates irreducibly ‘to heal’, ‘to reappropriate’, ‘to learn/teach again’, ‘to struggle’, to ‘become able to restore life where it was poisoned’, and it demands that we learn how to do it for each zone of devastation, each zone of the earth, of our collective practices and of our experience.⁶

To reclaim a grand narrative in this context would mean to create it again collectively, not as anonymous, universal subjects without any attachments to the planet Earth, but as people who are anchored in a specific place and time. It would mean to think from within a positionality that is at once physical, political and affective.

As Lyotard rightly pointed out, the old grand narratives have lost their efficacy. Yet, instead of abandoning the format completely as countless poststructuralist, postcolonial and feminist thinkers have advocated, it is time, I believe, to reinvent them – both in terms

⁵ On the importance of grand narratives for political and social life see, notably, F. Jameson, *The Political Unconscious: Narrative as a Socially Symbolic Act* (London and New York: Routledge, 1981); F. Jameson, ‘Foreword’, in Lyotard, *The Postmodern Condition*, pp. vii–xxi.

⁶ I. Stengers, ‘Experimenting with refrains: Subjectivity and the challenge of escaping modern dualism’, *Subjectivity* 22 (1) (2008): 58.

of their content and in the circumstances of their articulation. We need new stories for a new age, told from where we are today. A handful of contemporary philosophers are already undertaking this project. This is the case, for instance, with Bruno Latour's conceptualisation of Gaïa, Peter Sloterdijk's spherology and Dipesh Chakrabarty's planetarity.⁷ This article, however, focuses on ecofeminism as a particularly valuable philosophical resource that has long been overlooked and underappreciated. Whilst planetarity is the theoretical framework most frequently employed in discussions on climate change in environmental humanities, this article mobilises instead the concept of cohabitability. Cohabitability focuses on the conditions for sustaining life on Earth (habitability), emphasising collaboration with more-than-human actors to bring this about (co-). The framework of cohabitability does not zoom out to the level of the planet in a way that would cancel the specificities of places and human-nonhuman collectivities. Rather, it always considers local attachments and infrastructures for maintaining liveable conditions. Cohabitability is compatible with ecofeminism because the question of the habitability of the planet Earth is at the heart of ecofeminist activism and philosophy. Ecofeminists ask how we can inhabit the planet in a life-affirming way. Their forms of living, organising and theorising prefigure liveable modes of cohabitation with other-than-human worlds. Briefly put, cohabitability lies at the heart of

⁷ On innovative ecological grand narratives in the works of Peter Sloterdijk, Bruno Latour and Dipesh Chakrabarty, see I. Janicka, 'Ecological grand narratives: What new stories for an age of climate crisis?' *Topoi* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11245-025-10315-z>. In recent anthropology, scholars working on 'patchy Anthropocene' attempt to 'reclaim, in a new register, anthropology's heritage of daring to make big claims about humans and about the worlds' (A.L. Tsing, A.S. Mathews and N. Bubandt, 'Patchy Anthropocene: Landscape structure, multispecies history, and the retooling of anthropology. An introduction to supplement 20', *Current Anthropology* **60** (20) (2019): 187). Even though they do not mention grand narratives and are weary of big scales, they conceptualise 'patchy Anthropocene' as an 'imagined holism' (Tsing et al., 'Patchy Anthropocene', 190). See also A.L. Tsing et al., *Field Guide to the Patchy Anthropocene: The New Nature* (Stanford, California: Stanford University Press, 2024). We agree on the aim but differ on the conceptual trajectory.

ecofeminist practices. As a concept, it is more effective for the task at hand, allowing us to trace the coarticulations between humans and nonhumans that take place in ecofeminist activism.⁸

Ecofeminist grand narratives?

Ecofeminists have been proposing new ecological grand narratives for some time. Admittedly, this has not taken the form of any declared project (collective or otherwise), nor has such work been explicitly framed as the reclamation of grand narratives for the twenty-first century. Yet, I contend that this is precisely the tacit impulse that underpins much ecofeminist work. Indeed, this undercurrent has, I believe, driven most of the disputes between ecofeminists and poststructuralist feminists of the 1990s. Fractious debates about essentialism and unseemly spirituality – as ecofeminists have had a tendency to engage with spirituality and its practices both in their theorisation and activism – are deeply intertwined with the questions of universality that lie at the heart of grand narratives.

The concept of universality – of who counts as ‘all’ – is fundamental to Western philosophy and is posited as neutral (gender-less, race-less, class-less). However, as numerous feminist and critical-race philosophers have argued, philosophy is itself traditionally coded as male, white and Western.⁹ Such categories likewise mark the concept of universality. Many thinkers have, quite rightly, strongly rebutted the notion of the white male as representative of universality. As a consequence, uni-

⁸ On the difference between the frameworks of habitability and planetarity, see I. Janicka, ‘Habitability: Planetarity vs cosmopolitics’, *Migrating Minds* 2 (1) (2024): 4–25. On ‘coarticulation’, see I. Janicka, ‘Coarticulation: Mutual transformation in human and nonhuman relations’, *SubStance* 53 (2) (2024): 38–58. On ecofeminism as offering practical and philosophical models of cohabitation, see I. Janicka, ‘Ecofeminism for the 99%—Three theses’, *Coils of the Serpent* 15 (2025): 1–17.

⁹ S. de Beauvoir, *The Second Sex*, trans. by Constance Bore and Sheila Malovany-Chevallier (London: Vintage Classic, 2015 [1949]); G. Lloyd, *Man of Reason: ‘Male’ and ‘Female’ in Western Philosophy* (London: Routledge, 1984); J.A. Kourany, *Philosophy in a Feminist Voice. Critiques and Reconstructions* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1997); A. Graneß, *Philosophie in Afrika: Herausforderungen einer Globalen Philosophiegeschichte* (Berlin: Suhrkamp, 2023).

versality has been deemed to be an unsalvageable concept that must be rejected wholesale.¹⁰ Yet, universality is fundamentally a question about politics: how to create a community and with whom to create it? Who counts as a political subject, capable of actively participating in a collective effort? These are questions that we must ask if we wish to engage in politics. Ecofeminism poses the question of universality once more, albeit implicitly, in that it probes the role of nonhumans in our conceptualisation of universality. How are we attached and affected by nonhuman others? How do we become who we are, in collaboration with the entities that affect us and constitute us? Ecofeminism, as this article will show, allows us to recuperate the sullied term of universality, moving towards a new notion of ‘grounded universality’ – or perhaps what could be more aptly termed ‘grounded pluriversality’ – that makes space for other modes of existence, including the nonhuman.

Ecofeminism – or ecological feminism – is a combination of environmental thinking (eco) and women’s liberation (feminism), with the latter nowadays understood in a more inclusive sense than its initial formation, encompassing the liberation of various genders from patriarchal oppressions. Ecofeminism stems primarily from activism in the late 1970s that can be characterised as anti-nuclear, pacifist and environmental that achieved its highpoint in the 1980s and early 1990s. The movement developed in different places (USA, Australia, India and Europe, specifically Germany, Italy, UK, France) more or less simultaneously.¹¹ After a period of prolonged marginalisation in the early 2000s, ecofeminism is currently experiencing a considerable

¹⁰ S. Wynter, ‘Unsettling the coloniality of being/power/truth/freedom: Towards the human, after man, its overrepresentation—An argument’, *CR: The New Centennial Review* 3 (3) (2003): 257–337; K. Yusoff, *A Billion Black Anthropocenes or None* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2018).

¹¹ On the history of the movement, see A. Salleh, *Ecofeminism as Politics: Nature, Marx and the Postmodern* (ZED: London, 1997); N. Moore, *The Changing Nature of Ecofeminism: Telling Stories from Clayoquot Sound* (Vancouver: UBC Press, 2015); N. Moore, ‘Eco/feminist genealogies: Renewing promises and new possibilities’, in M. Phillips and N. Rumens (eds), *Contemporary Perspectives on Ecofeminism* (London: Routledge, 2016), pp.19–37; N. Sturgeon, ‘Ecofeminist movements’, in C. Merchant (ed.), *Ecology: Key Concepts in Critical Theory*, 2nd ed. (Amherst, NY: Humanities Books, 2008), pp. 237–49.

revival in both scholarship and activism.¹² The basic tenet of ecofeminism is that the subjugation of women – as well as of colonised and racialised subjects – is directly connected to the subjugation of nature. Indeed, scholarship shows that subjects marginalised along gender lines have much to teach us about the ecological oppression(s) of climate change. Notably, women make up sixty to eighty per cent of grassroots environmental organisations' membership and are more active in environmental projects than men.¹³ Women consider the impact of climate change to be more severe,¹⁴ and are more sceptical about top-down, purely technology-driven climate change solutions, tending instead to choose solutions based on alternative forms of living and relating to the world. What is more, they are more willing to shift to a more climate-friendly lifestyle.¹⁵ At the same time,

¹² For example, Françoise d'Eaubonne's seminal work *Feminism or Death*, originally published in French in 1974, was finally translated into English in 2022 (F. d'Eaubonne, *Feminism or Death. How the Women's Movement Can Save the Planet*, trans. by Ruth Hottell and Emma Ramadan (London: Verso, 2022 [1974]). Likewise, ecofeminism was recently the subject of a major exhibition showcasing the movement's rich histories and future-oriented developments: *Re/Sisters: A Lens on Gender and Ecology* (Barbican Centre, London, UK; 5 Oct. 2023–1 Jan. 2024). On the recent revival of ecofeminism, see also A. Isla (ed.) *Climate Chaos: Ecofeminism and the Land Question* (Toronto: Inanna Publications, 2019); E. Hache, 'Introduction: Reclaim ecofeminism!', in E. Hache (ed.), *Reclaim. Recueil de textes écoféministes* (Paris: Editions Cambourakis, 2016), pp. 13–57; G. Pruvost, *Quotidien politique: Féminisme, écologie, subsistance* (Paris: La Découverte, 2021); M. Phillips and N. Rumens (eds) *Contemporary Perspectives on Ecofeminism* (London: Routledge, 2016); M. Phillips, 'Reconnecting with nature: An ecofeminist view of environmental management', *Geographical Research* 58 (2) (2020): 154–66; N. Detraz, *Women and Climate Change: Examining Discourses from the Global North* (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 2023).

¹³ C. Ergas and R. York, 'Women's status and carbon dioxide emissions: A quantitative cross-national analysis', *Social Science Research* 41 (2012): 965–76.

¹⁴ G. Alber and U. Roehr, 'Climate protection: What's gender got to do with it?', *Women & Environments International Magazine* 70 (71) (2006): 17–20.

¹⁵ It is worth pointing out that this is in a stark contrast to the Christian idea of women as weak-willed and credulous (being led by the snake), as was described in the story of Eden above. Here we see ecofeminist women as more sceptical and invested in political action, willing to challenge top-down structures and change their living habits to combat climate change. An ecofeminist vision of a woman is radically different to the one in the story of Eden.

women and their issues are severely underrepresented in areas of climate change policy.¹⁶ Their voices remain deprioritised, if not outright silenced. Such disregard is inhibiting national and international action in effectively addressing climate change. From an ecofeminist perspective, in order to address the ecological crisis, we need to address the power imbalances in the world that are based on gender and racial discrimination. We need to address the bigger structures and their interrelations. Climate crisis is not merely a scientific problem (an issue of Earth's physiology that can be solved by technological means), but also a social, political and philosophical problem rooted in the fundamental structuring of our social world, and the power imbalances that continue to dominate. For this reason, technological and scientific approaches will never be sufficient to adequately address climate change in a truly fair and just way: approaches from the arts and humanities are equally crucial.

A return to ecofeminism has been a long time coming; the field has had a challenging trajectory. Ecofeminism has been marginalised not only in mainstream philosophy and the history of socio-political movements but also within feminist philosophy. Few movements have been as violently criticised.¹⁷ Ecofeminist work has been underrepresented in scholarly debates, understudied and undervalued. The rejection of ecofeminism by feminist philosophy in the late twentieth century can, arguably, be credited largely to the intellectual zeitgeist, rather than any fundamental philosophical flaws within ecofeminism itself. Specifically, the confluence of postmodernism, poststructuralist feminism and neoliberal feminism in academia in the 1980s and 1990s created a hostile environment for activist and 'affirmative' ecofeminism that tried to build a habitable world – both in theory and on the ground – rather than focusing primarily on critique. Indeed, as noted above, in a time when postmodern 'in-

¹⁶ Alber and Roehr, 'Climate protection'; Detraz, *Women and Climate Change*; G. Gaard, 'Ecofeminism and climate change', *Women's Studies International Forum* 49 (2015): 20–33.

¹⁷ Hache, 'Introduction'; C. Cuomo, *Feminism and Ecological Communities. An Ethic of Flourishing* (London: Routledge, 1997); A. Echols, *Daring to Be Bad: Radical Feminism in America 1967–1975* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1989).

credulity toward metanarratives¹⁸ defined the intellectual condition, ecofeminists' tacit gesture towards new 'grand narratives' triggered a vehement backlash from key feminist intellectuals of the time. At the same time, the new *working girl* model of neoliberal femininity severely undermined the credibility of the radical feminisms of the 1960s and 1970s.¹⁹ Finally, any conceptual apparatus regarding women and nature that bore even a passing resemblance to the idea of 'essence' was highly problematic to poststructuralists.²⁰ This was because it was read as a reactionary attempt to return women to their bodies, an idea that other feminists had been trying very hard to move away from. As certain ecofeminist scholars have argued, accusations of essentialism and tawdry spirituality – judged to be irrelevant and anti-intellectual – did not accurately describe the philosophical stakes of ecofeminism but operated all too frequently as a political 'smokescreen', concealing larger issues within feminism that concerned questions of embodiment and materiality.²¹ It is in

¹⁸ Lyotard, *The Postmodern Condition*.

¹⁹ I. Cambourakis, "Mise au poing": L'Engagement en radicalité de Françoise d'Eaubonne', in F. d'Eaubonne and I. Cambourakis (eds), *Contre-violence ou la résistance à l'Etat* (Paris: Editions Cambourakis, 2022), pp. 11–140.

²⁰ On the debate around essentialism in feminism, see N. Schor and E. Weed (eds), *The Essential Difference* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1994).

²¹ T. de Lauretis, 'Upping the anti (sic) in feminist theory', in M. Hirsch and E.F. Keller (eds), *Conflicts in Feminism* (New York: Routledge, 1990), pp. 255–70; E. Carlassare, 'Essentialism in ecofeminist discourse', in C. Merchant (ed.), *Ecology: Key Concepts in Critical Theory* (New Jersey: Humanities Press, 1997), pp. 220–34; Cuomo, *Feminism and Ecological Communities*; Moore, *The Changing Nature of Ecofeminism*. However, there has been an important critique of early ecofeminists as appropriating Indigenous knowledge: see G. Gaard, 'Ecofeminism and native American cultures: Pushing the limits of cultural imperialism?', in G. Gaard (ed.), *Ecofeminism: Women, Animals, Nature*, (Philadelphia: Temple University Press, 1993), pp. 295–314; N. Sturgeon, 'The nature of race: Discourses of racial difference in ecofeminism', in K.J. Warren (ed.), *Ecofeminism: Women, Culture, Nature* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1997), pp. 260–78. In recent years, ecofeminism has been more inclusive of Indigenous women's perspectives: see G. Gaard and P. Murphy (eds), *Ecofeminist Literary Criticism: Theory, Interpretation, Pedagogy* (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1998); A.E. Lucas, 'No remedy for the Inuit: Accountability for environmental harms under U.S. and

this context that I argue that ecofeminism is not an embarrassing blip in feminist theorising but an extremely valuable contribution to rethinking our collective human condition on Earth today. In fact, we need to reclaim ecofeminism not only for feminist philosophy but also for environmental philosophy more generally.

Ecofeminists propose different narratives about what it means to be a human being and how we are interrelated with the world. Instead of the idea of human beings as autonomous – one of the key tenets of modern philosophy²² – ecofeminists propose an interdependent human being that cannot be conceived beyond its material base (the body she occupies, the air she breathes, the soil she relies on to produce food) and the practices of cooperating with nature to benefit both the human and the nonhuman. Perhaps most importantly, they offer a set of practices to implement this vision collectively. Ecofeminists demonstrate prefiguratively an alternative, life-affirming way to inhabit the world.²³ If we assume that our contemporary ecological crisis is a problem of ‘habitat’ – in the sense that our ways of inhabiting the world are in crisis²⁴ – then it becomes

international Law’, in R. Stein (ed.), *New Perspectives on Environmental Justice: Gender, Sexuality, and Activism* (New Brunswick and London: Rutgers University Press, 2004), pp. 191–206; A. Sempértegui, ‘Indigenous women’s activism, ecofeminism, and extractivism: Partial connections in the Ecuadorian Amazon’, *Politics & Gender* 17 (2021): 197–224.

²² See on this, notably, A. Cavarero, *Inclinations: A Critique of Rectitude*, trans. by Amanda Minervini and Adam Sitze (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2016).

²³ On some of these practices, see especially B. Epstein, *Political Protest and Cultural Revolution: Nonviolent Direct Action in the 1970s and 1980s* (Berkeley: University of California, 1991); Moore, *The Changing Nature of Ecofeminism*.

²⁴ On such an approach to ecological crisis as a problem of habitability, see in particular the works of: B. Latour and P. Weibel (eds), *Critical Zones: The Science and Politics of Landing on Earth* (Karlsruhe: ZKM, Center for Art and Media Karlsruhe, 2020); P. Sloterdijk, *Spheres. Volume I: Bubbles. Microspherology*, trans. by Wieland Hoban (Los Angeles: Semiotext(e), 2011 [1998]); P. Sloterdijk, *Spheres. Volume II: Globes. Microspherology*, trans. by Wieland Hoban (Los Angeles: Semiotext(e), 2014 [1999]); P. Sloterdijk, *Spheres. Volume III: Foams. Plural Spherology*, trans. by Wieland Hoban (Los Angeles: Semiotext(e), 2016 [2004]); I. Stengers, *In Catastrophic Times: Resisting the Coming Barbarism*, trans. by Andrew Goffrey (London: Open Humanities Press, Meson Press, 2015 [2009]).

clear that feminist ecological thinkers²⁵ and activists propose a different, more sustainable and life-affirming, way of inhabiting the world than the vision proffered by capitalist Modernity.²⁶ The ecofeminist focus is on the reproduction of life as a whole, emphasising practices of sustenance, care, communality, repair and healing. Ecofeminists see themselves as interdependent with nature: they focus on sustainable forms of living and thriving on our planet, act in mutual aid and cross-species solidarity, embody direct democratic political processes by organising in egalitarian and non-discriminatory ways and connect means to ends by creating the world in which they want to live in the here and now.²⁷

Generativity-subsistence vs productivity-growth

It is simply impossible to do justice to the rich and diverse traditions of ecofeminism in a single article. As such, a particularly productive example from the new generation of French ecofeminist thinkers will have to suffice: Emilie Hache's *De la génération. Enquête sur sa disparition et son remplacement par la production* [*On generation. An investigation into its disappearance and replacement by production*] (2024).²⁸ Hache's work is especially noteworthy not only because of how it reworks the ecofeminist tradition but also because of its own

²⁵ I use 'ecofeminist' and 'ecological feminist' as synonyms. On the debate over such terminology, see C. Mallory, 'What's in a name? In defence of ecofeminism (not ecological feminisms, feminist ecology, or gender and the environment)', *Ethics and the Environment* 23 (2) (2018): 11–35.

²⁶ In this context, see S. Federici, *Caliban and the Witch: Women, the Body and Primitive Accumulation* (New York: Autonomedia; London: Pluto, 2014); C. Merchant, *The Death of Nature: Women, Ecology and the Scientific Revolution* (London: Wildwood House, 1980); J.W. Moore, *Capitalism in the Web of Life: Ecology and the Accumulation of Capital* (London: Verso, 2015).

²⁷ Ecofeminist practices have much in common with anarchist practices: see Epstein, *Political Protest and Cultural Revolution*.

²⁸ E. Hache, *De la génération. Enquête sur sa disparition et son remplacement par la production* (Paris: La Découverte, 2024).

engaged ecofeminist methodology. The book gestures towards the futures of ecofeminism: how ecofeminism can be further developed in order to make our more-than-human worlds more liveable.

The French philosopher proposes a counter-narrative to (re)orient our contemporary extractivist and productivist societies, which are not concerned by the conditions of existence that allow life to continue, but rather operate according to the values of economic growth, progress and productivity. Hache argues, following Sylvia Federici²⁹ and Carolyn Merchant,³⁰ that the metanarrative of Modernity made us forget that we need continuous practices of generation and regeneration in order to exist. While the paradigm of productivity in our industrial societies presupposes the exploitation of the living world without limits – an infinite growth without consequences – Hache claims that we need to reconstruct a mode of thinking of *génération* ('generation' or 'generativity'), which would focus on recreating the conditions of habitability on Earth. On her reading, generation as a paradigm for collective living has been effectively wiped out from contemporary Western cultures. It can only be partly reconstructed from distant fragments found in pre-industrial and non-industrial societies, in Ancient Greece, medieval Europe and certain contemporary matrilineal societies. Virtually all traces of generative thinking (and living) have disappeared and, thus, Hache is obliged to engage in an act of speculative reconstruction that weaves together history, mythology and theology to create the preconditions for reimagining a different collective destiny. In order to be able to imagine the future, we need to reconstruct the past. In Hache's reading, generation is always already a regeneration. It is a reproduction of the conditions of habitability and a process of healing, repair and maintenance. That is why she uses the term '(re)generation'. Hache demonstrates the vital importance of (re)generative practices responsible for ensuring the renewal of society as a whole – subsistence work, reproductive labour and links with the unseen. She shows that the advent of Christianity instituted a new relationship with the world. Concern with the (re)

²⁹ Federici, *Caliban and the Witch*.

³⁰ Merchant, *The Death of Nature*.

generation of the world was gradually replaced by the idea that the world was created once and for all, the finite action of a divine being. The everyday work of taking care of things and people, and thereby perpetuating life, was no longer posited as necessary. In modernity, women and nature were effectively side-lined as the principle of generativity was being replaced by productivity.

Strikingly, and somewhat provocatively, Hache turns to the question of matriarchy to trace an alternative vision of the world. Regardless of the debates about the actual existence of matriarchies, the philosopher speculatively reconstructs what matriarchy *could* mean in practice for our societies. She redefines matriarchy not as a system in which women (rather than men) dominate in a society, as it is often understood. Rather, Hache proposes that matriarchy is a system which centres (re)generation, the base of a cosmology that determines the values and the modes of operation of a world.³¹ Although no mention is made of grand narratives – not the least because Hache works within poststructuralist and pragmatist traditions – the philosopher is, indeed, engaged in an effort to offer us an alternative macro-level narrative about where we stand in respect to each other and to the nonhuman world. She calls explicitly for a ‘new myth’ (“nouveau” mythe³²) and claims that we need to ‘nurture ... a mythology relevant for our time’.³³ New metanarratives – even those labelled as ‘myths’ – aim at reshaping our attitudes to the world. They tell us that we are obligated to undertake constant activities of renewal, repair and maintenance to sustain life on Earth.³⁴

³¹ Hache, *De la génération*, pp. 203, 209.

³² *Ibid.*, p. 63.

³³ My translation of ‘nourrir ... une mythologie adéquate à notre temps’ (Hache, *De la génération*, p. 34).

³⁴ Scholarly work on maintenance and repair has been flourishing in recent years: see, notably, A. Crosby and J. Adams Stein, ‘Repair’, *Environmental Humanities* 12 (1) (2020): 179–85; S. Mattern, ‘Maintenance and care’, *Places Journal* (Nov. 2018), placesjournal.org/article/maintenance-and-care/ (accessed 20 Jan. 2026); D. Papadopoulos, M. Puig de la Bellacasa and M. Tacchetti (eds), *Ecological Reparation: Repair, Remediation and Resurgence in Social and Environmental Conflict* (Bristol: Bristol University Press, 2023).

In this way, Hache accomplishes a performative and creative gesture. The ecofeminist story she relays is a story in which humans *inhabit* a common space with others, including nonhuman beings, and are considered *from* their environments (air, soil, more-than-human collectives) rather than from the essence that they purportedly inherently possess (*logos*, agency, free will, moral action). Humans, like other beings, are generated by their environments (social, technological, natural) and are integral parts of these environments. This is an important shift in philosophy that reconfigures what it means to be a human in an ecological age. A new vocabulary for rearticulating human–nonhuman relationships is developed. What is particularly important in ecofeminist approaches is their focus on situatedness³⁵ or what Geneviève Pruvost terms a ‘grounded day-to-day’ (*quotidienneté ancrée*).³⁶ This means that (re)generation can never be detached from where the work of subsistence is happening. In an ecofeminist framework, the basic political and ethical questions are: who is taking care of the conditions that are necessary to perpetuate life? What activities are worthy of being undertaken on a daily basis (and in perpetuity), so that they make a more-than-human collective more capable and life-affirming? What sort of day-to-day life is worth living and maintaining?

As remarked upon above, grand narratives fundamentally pose a question of universality. Universality, in turn, is a question about politics, about who is part of a ‘we’ and what holds us together as a body politic. Universality may be an uncomfortable question, given the concept’s history, but it is clear that it is, nevertheless, an inescapable one. The problematic and exclusionary patterns underpinning the traditional notion of universality do not need to be – and indeed, must not be – replicated. In place of universality, we can think of ‘grounded pluriversality’ to make space for other, also non-

³⁵ ‘Situatenedness’ and ‘situated knowledges’ considerably influenced debates in feminism, critical posthumanism and environmental humanities. See a seminal text by D. Haraway, ‘Situatened knowledges: The science question in feminism and the privilege of partial perspective’, *Feminist Studies* 14 (3) (1988): 575–99.

³⁶ Pruvost, *Quotidien politique*, p. 7.

human, modes of existence. Pluriversality points to the multiplicity of various worlds and to what is *in common* – yet not the same – across difference.³⁷ It is not an abstract philosophical concept but a lived negotiation between radically different beings (humans, plants, animals, soil) towards a life-affirming cohabitation. In light of the climate crisis and the rapid development of technologies, it is more important than ever to ask about the role of nonhumans in our conceptualisation of universality.³⁸ By ‘complicating our universals’,³⁹ we can account more accurately for our hybrid (human-nonhuman) political communities in the twenty-first century.

More-than-human cohabitability

The climate crisis rages and threatens to incinerate familiar structures of ways of being in the world. We must reshape our practices, our politics and our thinking in order to respond effectively. It is for this reason, then, that I argue that we must turn to ecofeminism in order to develop a new concept of politics – specifically the ‘politics of cohabitability’ – that considers nonhumans to be an integral part of politics and thereby allows us to reconsider our political practices with nonhumans. This task can be understood as the reformulation of habitability from a feminist point of view, supporting the crea-

³⁷ On pluriversality, see in particular an examination of different modes of existence in B. Latour, *An Inquiry into Modes of Existence: An Anthropology of the Moderns*, trans. by Catherine Porter (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2013). On the definition of universality from within more-than-human approaches, specifically in Latour and Stengers, see I. Janicka, ‘The Janus face of cosmopolitics. The concept of universality in Isabelle Stengers and Bruno Latour’, *Philosophy Today* **68** (1) (2024): 129–45. For further elaboration of ‘grounded pluriversality’ in ecofeminism, see Janicka, ‘Ecofeminism for the 99%’.

³⁸ On the interplay of universality and particularity in ecofeminism, see G.Y. Kao, ‘The universal versus the particular in ecofeminist ethics’, *The Journal of Religious Ethics* **38** (4) (2010): 616–37.

³⁹ B. Cassin, *Sophistical Practice: Toward a Consistent Relativism* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2014 [1995]); B. Cassin, *Éloge de la traduction. Compliquer l’universel* (Paris: Fayard, 2016).

tion of a philosophical framework to articulate an ecofeminist mode of human-nonhuman cohabitation on a grand scale. Or, more succinctly, the formulation of an ecofeminist grand narrative.

Ecofeminism is crucial for us today because it offers a means of action, a way of *engaging* in politics rather than in abstracted critique. Ecofeminism is fundamentally a means of enactment that brings women – and other beings – back to life.⁴⁰ The tacit assumption of a ‘politics of cohabitability’ is that we live neither in a vacuum nor in a generic model (‘a society’, ‘a city’, ‘a village’, ‘an intentional community’) but always in a specific place populated by specific people, created by sedimented practices and anchored in a living environment.⁴¹ In order to update our key political concepts for an era of climate change (solidarity, community, freedom, emancipation, equality), we need to shift our emphasis to the material base of human existence. We need to consider such political terms as fundamentally *earthly* (as opposed to abstracted) issues of subsistence in which the question of location – where is human? – is the point of departure for rethinking our collective habitability.⁴² We need to link the philosophy of cohabitability to the everyday political questions of more-than-human cohabitation.

Ecofeminists have been actively pursuing such a practice for a long time. Indeed, they have been at the forefront of advocating and caring for the planet. We need to ask, then, what we can learn from ecofeminist movements across the world, both past and present, that could help us to redefine ourselves as human species and to act responsibly in the current age of climate crisis. What kind of a new philosophy of cohabitability on Earth in the twenty-first

⁴⁰ B. Zitouni, ‘Planetary destruction, ecofeminists and transformative politics in the early 1980s’, *Interface* 6 (2) (2014): 244–70.

⁴¹ Pruvost, *Quotidien politique*; J.K. Graham-Gibson, *The End of Capitalism (as We Know It)* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2006 [1996]).

⁴² P. Charbonnier, *Affluence and Freedom. An Environmental History of Political Ideas*, trans. by Andrew Brown (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2021 [2020]); K. Pomeranz, *The Great Divergence: China, Europe, and the Making of the Modern World Economy* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2000); Latour and Weibel, *Critical Zones*; Sloterdijk, *Spheres I–III*.

century can we conceptualise, if we listen and learn from feminist ecological philosophers and activists? It is important to note that we need a plurality of grand narratives rather than one single ecological grand narrative to encompass all questions. Ecofeminism offers one version of a more-than-human cohabitability. By reclaiming grand narratives with ecofeminism – and the tacit grand narratives of ecofeminism – we take a meaningful first step in the right direction.

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